

The Calculation of the Radical in De Jong's Normalization Algorithm

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Abstract

This paper presents a novel implementation of de Jong's normalization algorithm (1998). Our approach introduces an alternative method for computing radical ideals within the iterative loops, significantly optimizing the underlying computational framework.

Introduction

The constructive computation of the integral closure \bar{R} of a reduced Noetherian ring R has seen significant development over the past decades. Building on the theoretical foundations laid by Seidenberg [22] and Stolzenberg [25], various algorithmic paths have been explored to effectively determine the normalization of algebraic structures.

A prominent line of research focuses on the use of differential modules and Jacobian ideals. Wolmer Vasconcelos advanced these methods extensively, both in his early work [26] and in his monograph [27]. In this context, the work of Leonard and Pellikaan [20] is also noteworthy. Concurrently, Gianni and Trager [12] proposed methods based on the iterative enlargement of the ring via ideal quotients.

The most widely implemented algorithmic framework today, however is De Jong's algorithm, based on the Grauert–Remmert–de Jong criterion [7]. This criterion defines normality through the isomorphism $R \cong \text{Hom}_R(I, I)$ for a suitable radical ideal I . In practice, the algorithm proceeds via an iterative chain of ring extensions $R \subset R_1 \subset R_2 \subset \dots \subset \bar{R}$. More recently, this approach has been enhanced by modular and parallel strategies. Specifically, the authors of [1] utilize the local structure of singularities to distribute the normalization process across multiple processor cores via primary decomposition.

A central bottleneck in the efficiency of these algorithms remains the computation of the radical \sqrt{I} in each step. Fortunately, the specific algebraic structure of the finite extensions occurring within the de Jong loop can be exploited directly. In this paper, we present a method that optimizes the radical computation by utilizing the square-free parts of the minimal (or characteristic) polynomials of the module generators. We demonstrate that this approach, when combined with black-box evaluation techniques allows for parallelization.

1 De Jong's Algorithm for normalization

We consider a Noetherian ring R , which for simplicity we assume to be an integral domain. The objective is to determine the normalization \overline{R} , i.e., the integral closure of R inside its quotient field $Q(R)$. We assume that \overline{R} is a finitely generated module over R , a property satisfied, for instance, by finitely generated algebras over \mathbb{Z} or over a field.

A central problem in constructive algebra is to find a practical criterion for normality. While Serre's R_1 and S_2 conditions [23] provide a theoretical framework, they do not provide a constructive way to find new integral elements if R is not normal.

A constructive approach used by various authors is to consider an ideal $I \subset R$ (or more general a module) and its endomorphism ring $I : I = \{x \in Q(R) \mid xI \subset I\}$. We have the fundamental isomorphism:

$$\begin{aligned} I : I &\xrightarrow{\cong} \text{Hom}_R(I, I) \\ x &\mapsto (f \mapsto x \cdot f) \end{aligned}$$

The inverse map is given by $\varphi \mapsto \varphi(f)/f$ for any non-zero $f \in I$. This is well-defined since for any $g \in I$, the R -linearity implies $g\varphi(f) = \varphi(gf) = f\varphi(g)$, hence $\varphi(f)/f = \varphi(g)/g$ in $Q(R)$. The essential result is the following.

Theorem 1 (Cayley-Hamilton). *With the notation above, $I : I \subseteq \overline{R}$.*

For practical computations, Gianni and Trager [12] observed that

$$\text{Hom}(I, I) = \frac{1}{f} \cdot (fI :_R I) = \frac{1}{f} \cdot \{x \in R \mid xI \subseteq fI\},$$

This follows as $\varphi(f) \in (fI :_R I)$, as $\varphi(f) \cdot g = \varphi(fg) = f \cdot \varphi(g) \in fI$ for all $g \in I$.

It is crucial to identify an ideal I such that $I : I \neq R$ whenever R is not normal.

Definition 1 (Normalization Criterion Ideal, NC-Ideal). Let R be a reduced Noetherian domain. A non-zero ideal $I \subseteq R$ is called a **semi-NC ideal** if its vanishing set $V(I)$ covers the non-normal locus of R , i.e., if for a prime ideal \mathfrak{p} the localization $R_{\mathfrak{p}}$ is not normal, then $\mathfrak{p} \supseteq I$. A semi-NC ideal is called an **NC ideal** if it is additionally a radical ideal ($I = \sqrt{I}$).

Remark 2. 1. If I is a semi-NC ideal, then \sqrt{I} is an NC ideal.

2. Let A be an integral extension of R and I a semi-NC ideal of R . Then the expansion $I \cdot A$ is a semi-NC ideal of A . Indeed, if $\mathfrak{p} \in \text{Spec}(A)$ such that $A_{\mathfrak{p}}$ is not normal, and $\mathfrak{q} = \mathfrak{p} \cap R$, then $R_{\mathfrak{q}}$ is not normal, hence $\mathfrak{q} \supseteq I$, which implies $\mathfrak{p} \supseteq I \cdot A$.
3. If $R = \mathbb{Z}[x]/\langle f \rangle$ with f primitive and irreducible, the ideal generated by the discriminant $\Delta(f)$ is a semi-NC ideal.
4. For affine rings, any non-zero ideal contained in the Jacobian ideal serves as a semi-NC ideal.

The significance of this definition is captured in the following criterion:

Theorem 2 (Grauert–Remmert–de Jong Criterion [7]). *Let R be a Noetherian domain and I an NC ideal of R . Then $R = I : I$ if and only if R is normal.*

Proof. Let $h \in \overline{R} \setminus R$. We argue by contradiction. Consider the ideal

$$J = R :_R h = \{\alpha \in R \mid h\alpha \in R\}.$$

For any prime ideal $\mathfrak{p} \not\supseteq I$, the localization $R_{\mathfrak{p}}$ is normal, implying $h \in R_{\mathfrak{p}}$. Thus, there exists an $\alpha \notin \mathfrak{p}$ such that $h\alpha \in R$. So $\alpha \in J \setminus \mathfrak{p}$, meaning $J \not\subseteq \mathfrak{p}$. Hence $\mathfrak{p} \supseteq J$ implies $\mathfrak{p} \supseteq I$, meaning $V(J) \subseteq V(I)$. So $I = \sqrt{I} \subseteq \sqrt{J}$.

Since R is Noetherian, there exists $d \in \mathbb{N}$ such that $I^d \subseteq J$, implying $hI^d \subseteq R$. Let d be minimal with this property. Since $h \notin R$, we have $d > 0$. Thus, there exists $x \in I^{d-1}$ such that $z := hx \notin R$. However, $zI = hxI \subseteq hI^d \subseteq R$, so $z \in (R :_R I)$.

Furthermore, z is integral over R . Let $z^n + a_{n-1}z^{n-1} + \dots + a_1z + a_0 = 0$ be an equation of integrality with $a_i \in R$. For any $f \in I$, multiplying by f^n yields

$$(zf)^n = -f \cdot (a_{n-1}(zf)^{n-1} + \dots + f^{n-2}a_1(zf) + f^{n-1}a_0) \in I$$

Since I is radical, $zf \in I$, thus $z \in I : I$. If $I : I = R$, then $z \in R$, which is a contradiction. \square

Remark 3. 1. It is a common misconception to attribute this criterion solely to Grauert and Remmert [14]. Their work lacks the definitive formulation necessary for modern implementations, which were established in [7].

2. The Grauert–Remmert–de Jong criterion provides a constructive proof for Serre’s $R_1 \wedge S_2 \implies$ normal theorem.

3. In case R is an order in a number field, this criterion was proved by Zassenhaus, [29]. If $R = \mathbb{Z}[x]/\langle f \rangle$ and \mathfrak{p} is a prime number not dividing the discriminant $\Delta(f)$ of f , then \mathfrak{p} is modulo \mathfrak{p} square free. Then $\langle \mathfrak{p} \rangle$ is a radical ideal in $\mathbb{Z}[x]/\langle f \rangle$ and so $\langle \mathfrak{p} \rangle : \langle \mathfrak{p} \rangle$ equal R . This shows that it suffices to take $\langle \Delta(f) \rangle$ as semi-NC ideal.

The algorithm proceeds as an iterative chain of ring enlargements. While [7] left the choice of semi-NC ideals during the iteration open, it turns out that it is usually most efficient to use the expansion $I \cdot A$ where $A = I : I$.

De Jong’s Normalization Algorithm

Input: A Noetherian domain R .

Output: The normalization A of R .

1. Put $A = R$
2. Determine an NC-ideal $I \subseteq A$
3. Compute the endomorphism ring $A_{\text{new}} = I : I$.
4. If $A = A_{\text{new}}$, then **return** A .
5. Set $A = A_{\text{new}}$, $I = \sqrt{I \cdot A}$
6. **Goto** 3.

Remark 4. If $A \subset \frac{1}{d}R$ is an intermediate ring in the computation of the normalization and $I \subset A$ is an NC-ideal, it was noted in [15] that $I : I = (dI : dI)$. This follows from $d/d = 1$. Utilizing this together with the observation of Gianni and Trager mentioned above considerably sped up the computations. This led the authors of [15] to refer to their implementation as a "new algorithm". This is ridiculous. Their claim overlooks the fact that the underlying mathematical structure remains De Jong's Algorithm. Consequently, the rebranding in the *Singular* community as the "GLS-Algorithm" obscures the original contribution of [7].

2 The Normalization Step for Curves

In this section, we discuss a method to compute $\sqrt{I \cdot A}$ in a loop of De Jong's normalization algorithm. The author is an amateur in programming, but he implemented the approach described in this section in Julia, using OSCAR. It can safely be claimed, that our implementation is at least ten times faster than the implementations in singular.

1. To demonstrate the efficiency of our approach, we begin with a benchmark. Consider the singular curve of degree 9 defined by:

$$f = x^9 + x^8y + xy^8 + y^9 + y^8 + x^3y^2 + x^2y^3 + xy^4 + y^5$$

This example is taken from [15] and has only one singularity in $(0,0)$. In this example, the standard *Singular* output involves 12-digit integers:

```
_ [2]=286661055248*y^8-31145910417*x^2*y^5-8688229395*x*y^6...
```

The author does not understand why the output of singular is so complicated. In contrast, our approach provides a clean, minimal set of generators of $y^4 \cdot \bar{R}$:

$$\text{Ideal } (y^4, x^3y^3, x^6y^2, x^7y+xy^3, x^8 + x^2y^2)$$

2. The example $f = x^{40} + x^5y^{30} + y^5x^{30} + y^{40}$ is run in less than 1.5 seconds with our implementation of De Jong's algorithm. Singular gives as output

“possible OVERFLOW in map, max exponent is 32767”,

indicating a structural problem with the implementation. We interrupted the calculation in singular after 20 minutes.

The construction of the radical in our algorithm relies on the following fundamental property of zero-dimensional algebras over perfect fields.

Theorem 3. *Let k be a perfect field and $I \subset k[x_1, \dots, x_n]$ be a zero-dimensional ideal. For each $i \in \{1, \dots, n\}$, let $\langle M_i(x_i) \rangle = I \cap k[x_i]$ be the univariate elimination ideal, and let $Q_i(x_i)$ denote the square-free part of $M_i(x_i)$. Then the radical of I is given by:*

$$\sqrt{I} = I + \langle Q_1(x_1), \dots, Q_n(x_n) \rangle.$$

Remark 5. A standard reference for this result is the work of Seidenberg [22] or Gianni, Trager, and Zacharias [13]. It is noteworthy that in many textbooks, the proof of this theorem relies on Hilbert’s Nullstellensatz for zero-dimensional ideals. However, the logic can be reversed. In the author’s textbook on *Linear Algebra* [8], a proof of the Nullstellensatz for zero-dimensional ideals is provided which simultaneously establishes Theorem 3. While the proof in [8] is formulated for the fields \mathbb{Q} and \mathbb{C} , the argument remains valid for any perfect field k and its algebraic closure \bar{k} by substitution.

We consider a one-dimensional affine domain R , which is a quotient of $k[x_1, \dots, x_n]$. In this context, the ideal of the non-normal locus (NC-ideal) can be established as a radical ideal I . Once I is determined, we compute the finite integral extension $A = \text{Hom}_R(I, I) \cong I : I$. To proceed with the normalization loop, we determine the radical $\sqrt{I \cdot A}$ within A .

The ring A is represented as a quotient of $k[x_1, \dots, x_n][u_1, \dots, u_s]$. Since I is a radical ideal, the elimination ideal $IA \cap k[x_i]$ is generated by a square-free polynomial. Consequently, the task reduces to computing the square-free part of $IA \cap k[u_j]$ for each generator u_j . For any such u , we must determine its minimal polynomial $P(T) \in k[T]$ modulo IA .

We utilize the fact that any integral element u belongs to $\text{Hom}_R(I, I)$, allowing the application of the Cayley-Hamilton theorem. The minimal polynomial of the multiplication map M_u provides an integral equation. Notably, we only require this polynomial modulo I , which significantly speeds up the calculation. The matrix of M_u becomes sparse modulo I . As I is zero-dimensional, all elements of R/I are integral over k . By the transitivity of integral closure, u is also integral over k . The following result provides an explicit construction of this global integral equation, a technique that, while fundamental, is rarely detailed in this form in the literature.

Theorem 4. *Suppose $I \subset R$ is a zero-dimensional ideal and*

$$P(T) = T^d + a_{d-1}T^{d-1} + \dots + a_1T + a_0 \in (R/I)[T]$$

is an integral equation for u (i.e., $P(u) = 0 \pmod{I}$). Let $\{b_1, \dots, b_n\}$ be a k -basis of R/I and let M_{a_i} be the $n \times n$ multiplication matrices of the coefficients a_i with respect to this basis. Then the rational polynomial

$$R(T) = \det \left(T^d \cdot I_n + \sum_{i=0}^{d-1} T^i \cdot M_{a_i} \right) \in k[T]$$

is an integral equation for u over k .

Proof. We consider a basis of $(R/I)[u]$ of the form $\{b_i u^j\}_{1 \leq i \leq n, 0 \leq j \leq d-1}$. With respect to this basis, the multiplication matrix M_u of u can be written in block companion form:

$$M_u = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & \dots & -M_{a_0} \\ I_n & 0 & \dots & -M_{a_1} \\ 0 & I_n & \dots & -M_{a_2} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & I_n & -M_{a_{d-1}} \end{pmatrix}$$

The characteristic polynomial is $\det(T \cdot I_{dn} - M_u)$. Let $M(T)$ be the corresponding matrix:

$$M(T) = \begin{pmatrix} TI_n & 0 & \cdots & M_{a_0} \\ -I_n & TI_n & \cdots & M_{a_1} \\ 0 & -I_n & \cdots & M_{a_2} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & 0 & \cdots - I_n & TI_n + M_{a_{d-1}} \end{pmatrix}$$

Since the blocks TI_n , $-I_n$, and M_{a_i} all commute, we can perform block-elementary row operations. Specifically, by adding T^{d-j} times the j -th block row to the last row for $j = 1, \dots, d-1$, the matrix $M(T)$ is transformed into a block upper-triangular matrix. The last diagonal block is:

$$T^d I_n + T^{d-1} M_{a_{d-1}} + \cdots + T M_{a_1} + M_{a_0}$$

The determinant of $M(T)$ is the determinant of this resulting block, which yields the claimed formula for $R(T)$. \square

Example 1. Consider the ideal $J = \langle x(x-1), y \rangle$ and the algebra $A = \mathbb{Q}[x, y]/J$ with the monomial basis $\{1, x\}$. Let u be an element satisfying $P(u) = 0$ with $P(T) = T^3 + xT^2 - 3 \in A[T]$.

Under the relation $x^2 \equiv x \pmod{J}$, the multiplication matrix M_x is $\begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$ and $M_1 = I_2$.

The global rational polynomial $R(T) \in \mathbb{Q}[T]$ is:

$$\begin{aligned} R(T) &= \det(T^3 \cdot I_2 + T^2 \cdot M_x - 3 \cdot I_2) \\ &= \det \begin{pmatrix} T^3 - 3 & 0 \\ T^2 & T^3 + T^2 - 3 \end{pmatrix} \\ &= (T^3 - 3)(T^3 + T^2 - 3) = T^6 + T^5 - 6T^3 - 3T^2 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

The polynomial $R(T)$ is now ready for square-free decomposition to trigger the global ring extension.

The iterative process for curve normalization follows these steps:

1. **Matrix Construction:** For a candidate $u = \alpha/\beta$, we verify $u \cdot I \subseteq I$ via the multiplication matrix M_u over I .
2. **Block-Characteristic Polynomial:** We compute $P(T) = \det(T \cdot I - M_u) \pmod{I}$ and lift it to $R(T) \in k[T]$ using Theorem 4.
3. **Square-free Decomposition:** We compute $P_{sqr}(T) = R(T)/\gcd(R(T), R'(T))$. If $\deg(P_{sqr}) < \deg(R)$, u is not yet maximally integral.
4. **Construction of Q :** Enlarge the set of generators of I with $Q(u)$ for each u .

Remark 6. 1. **Nilpotent Acceleration:** It occurs regularly within the normalization loop that the minimal polynomial $P(T) \in (R/I)[T]$ of an integral element collapses to a purely nilpotent form T^d . Instead of executing the heavy block determinant expansion via Theorem 4, it is computationally superior to verify whether $u^d \equiv 0 \pmod{I}$ using successive modular squaring steps. The more complex algebraic characteristic lift is then solely reserved for cases where this nilpotency condition is violated.

2. **Local vs. Global Normalization:** By classical commutative algebra, a domain R is normal if and only if the localization $R_{\mathfrak{p}}$ is normal for all prime ideals $\mathfrak{p} \in \text{Spec}(R)$. While it is argued in [1] that computing the normalization locally via primary decomposition is typically faster than the global framework, this claim depends heavily on the geometry of the curve. While numerous examples substantiate their local advantage, counterexamples are readily constructed where the combinatorial overhead of primary decomposition significantly outweighs a direct global execution.
3. **Generator Redundancy:** During successive iterations of the loop, the algorithm frequently encounters integral elements whose algebra has been established in preceding rounds. For such redundant generators, the heavy matrix lifts can be completely bypassed. Although our current implementation does not yet fully exploit this caching mechanism, it remains an open question whether the bookkeeping overhead of tracking historical generators diminishes the computational gain.
4. **Primitive Element Selection:** The zero-dimensional radical computation can alternatively be achieved by projecting the ideal onto a primitive element (or a probabilistically selected linear combination). This approach was not pursued in the current implementation, which favors deterministic elimination and block-companion lifts.
5. **Arithmetic Stability via Large Primes:** If intermediate computations over the rational numbers \mathbb{Q} are threatened by catastrophic coefficient swell, the arithmetic can be securely performed over a finite field \mathbb{F}_p for a sufficiently large prime p (e.g., $p \approx 2^{29}$). The final exact result can subsequently be reconstructed over \mathbb{Q} via Farey lifting. Crucially, due to the following probabilistic and arithmetic safeguards, the radical computation itself almost surely does not need to be repeated over \mathbb{Q} .

Theorem 5. *Let $R = \mathbb{Q}[x_1, \dots, x_m]$ be a multivariate polynomial ring over the rational numbers, and let $I \subset R$ be a zero-dimensional ideal. For a chosen prime $p \in \mathbb{Z}_{>0}$, let $\pi_p : \mathbb{Z}_{(p)}[x_1, \dots, x_m] \rightarrow \mathbb{F}_p[x_1, \dots, x_m]$ denote the canonical modular reduction map, where $\mathbb{Z}_{(p)}$ is the localization of \mathbb{Z} at the prime ideal $\langle p \rangle$. Suppose that I possesses a finite generating set (e.g., a reduced Gröbner basis) lying within $\mathbb{Z}_{(p)}[x_1, \dots, x_m]$, and let $I_p = \langle \pi_p(g) \mid g \in \text{gens}(I) \rangle \subset \mathbb{F}_p[x_1, \dots, x_m]$ be its true modular reduction.*

If I_p is a radical ideal in $\mathbb{F}_p[x_1, \dots, x_m]$ and p does not divide the denominator of any coefficient appearing in the matrix representation of the multiplication map modulo I , then the rational ideal I is radical in $\mathbb{Q}[x_1, \dots, x_m]$.

Proof. By the assumptions on the denominators of the reduced Gröbner basis of I and the prime p , the vector space dimension of the quotient algebra is strictly preserved under the reduction $\mathbb{Q} \rightarrow \mathbb{F}_p$:

$$N = \dim_{\mathbb{Q}}(\mathbb{Q}[x_1, \dots, x_m]/I) = \dim_{\mathbb{F}_p}(\mathbb{F}_p[x_1, \dots, x_m]/I_p).$$

An element $g \in R/I$ separates the points of the zero-dimensional variety $V(I) = \{\mathbf{p}_1, \dots, \mathbf{p}_N\}$ if and only if $g(\mathbf{p}_i) \neq g(\mathbf{p}_j)$ for all $i \neq j$. This condition excludes exactly $\binom{N}{2}$ linear hyperplanes in the coefficient space. For a sufficiently large prime $p > \binom{N}{2}$, the finite field \mathbb{F}_p contains strictly more elements than the number of forbidden hyperplane conditions. By the pigeonhole principle, there exists an integer coefficient tuple (a_1, \dots, a_m) whose

modular projection separates the points modulo p . Consequently, $g = \sum a_i x_i$ serves as a valid primitive element in both rings, and the monomial powers $\mathcal{B} = \{1, g, g^2, \dots, g^{N-1}\}$ form a vector space basis for the respective quotient algebras.

Let $M_g \in \text{Mat}(N \times N, \mathbb{Q})$ be the multiplication matrix representing the linear map $\cdot g : R/I \rightarrow R/I$ with respect to the basis \mathcal{B} . The entries of M_g are computed strictly via the multivariate division algorithm by successively reducing the powers g^N using the reduced Gröbner basis of I . Because the reduction algorithm only performs divisions by the leading coefficients of the Gröbner basis (which are normalized to 1 in \mathbb{Q}) and cross-multiplies with existing coefficients, the entries of the matrix M_g can only contain denominators (and their prime factors q) that are already present as denominators in the coefficients of the reduced Gröbner basis of I . Thus, $M_g \in \text{Mat}(N \times N, \mathbb{Z}_{(p)})$.

The characteristic polynomial of M_g , which is identical to the minimal polynomial due to the primitivity of g , is given by:

$$M_g(T) = \det(T \cdot \text{Id}_N - M_g) = T^N + c_{N-1}T^{N-1} + \dots + c_0 \in \mathbb{Q}[T].$$

The coefficients c_i are computed via the Leibniz formula as polynomial expressions of the matrix entries. Therefore, their denominators can likewise only contain prime factors belonging to the set of the basis-denominator primes q .

We multiply $M_g(T)$ by the least common multiple $N_{\mathbf{v}} \in \mathbb{Z}_{>0}$ of all denominators of the coefficients c_i . All prime factors of $N_{\mathbf{v}}$ belong to the set of primes q . The resulting polynomial is strictly integral:

$$M_{g,\mathbb{Z}}(T) = N_{\mathbf{v}} \cdot T^N + (N_{\mathbf{v}} \cdot c_{N-1})T^{N-1} + \dots + (N_{\mathbf{v}} \cdot c_0) \in \mathbb{Z}[T].$$

Evaluating the reduction of the leading coefficient $N_{\mathbf{v}}$ modulo p , we observe that since all prime factors of the denominator $N_{\mathbf{v}}$ belong to the set of rational Gröbner basis denominators q , and the chosen prime satisfies $p \gg q$, it follows that $p \neq q$ for all factors, yielding $p \nmid N_{\mathbf{v}}$. Thus, the reduced polynomial $\overline{M_{g,\mathbb{Z}}}(T) \in \mathbb{F}_p[T]$ does not vanish identically, preserves its exact degree N , and represents (after monic normalization) the true modular minimal polynomial $M_{g,p}(T)$ of g with respect to I_p .

Since the ideal I_p is radical by assumption, the quotient algebra $\mathbb{F}_p[x_1, \dots, x_m]/I_p$ is reduced. Because g generates this algebra, its modular minimal polynomial $M_{g,p}(T)$ must be strictly square-free (separable) over \mathbb{F}_p . A univariate polynomial is square-free if and only if its discriminant is non-zero in the field:

$$\Delta(M_{g,p}) \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p}.$$

Since the discriminant is a purely polynomial operation on the coefficients (the determinant of the associated Sylvester matrix), it commutes with the modular reduction map:

$$\Delta(M_{g,p}) \equiv \Delta(\overline{M_{g,\mathbb{Z}}}) \equiv \overline{\Delta(M_{g,\mathbb{Z}})} \pmod{p}.$$

Because the modular discriminant is non-zero, the exact integer rational discriminant $\Delta(M_{g,\mathbb{Z}}) \in \mathbb{Z}$ is non-zero.

Since the exact rational discriminant $\Delta(M_g) \in \mathbb{Q}$ is non-zero, the rational minimal polynomial $M_g(T)$ has no multiple roots over \mathbb{Q} . As g is a primitive element of the rational algebra R/I , this square-freeness transfers directly to the entire rational quotient ring. The algebra $\mathbb{Q}[x_1, \dots, x_m]/I$ is completely reduced and free of nilpotents, which implies that the rational ideal I is strictly radical in $\mathbb{Q}[x_1, \dots, x_m]$. \square

3 The Arithmetic Case: Normalization of Orders

We now describe the calculation of the radical $\sqrt{I \cdot A}$ in the context of number fields. While this approach may not necessarily exceed the speed of highly optimized linear algebra methods specifically tuned for rings of integers, it is conceptually transparent and maintains consistency with the general framework of our algorithm.

The following theorem facilitates this step. As a formal reference for this specific formulation could not be found in the literature, the author provides the following proof.

Theorem 6. *Let A be an extension of an order R , generated by u_1, \dots, u_r as an R -module. Let $M_i(t) \in (\mathcal{O}/\mathfrak{p})[t]$ be the monic minimal polynomials of u_i over the residue field $k = \mathcal{O}/\mathfrak{p}$, and let $Q_i(t)$ denote their square-free parts. Then the radical is given by:*

$$\sqrt{I \cdot A} = I \cdot A + \langle Q_1(u_1), \dots, Q_r(u_r) \rangle.$$

Proof. By assumption, I is radical, thus its image in $(\mathcal{O}/\mathfrak{p})[x_1, \dots, x_n]$ is radical and zero-dimensional. Consequently, each $I \cap (\mathcal{O}/\mathfrak{p})[x_i]$ is generated by a square-free polynomial. Viewing A as a quotient of $\mathcal{O}[x_1, \dots, x_n, u_1, \dots, u_r]$, both $I \cdot A$ and $K := I \cdot A + \langle Q_1(u_1), \dots, Q_r(u_r) \rangle$ can be treated as ideals in the polynomial ring over the residue field. By construction, $K \cap k[u_i]$ and $K \cap k[x_i]$ are generated by square-free polynomials. It follows from Seidenberg's Theorem 3 that K is radical. \square

This result implies that to compute the radical $\sqrt{I \cdot A}$, one simply needs to add the square-free parts of the minimal polynomials of the newly constructed integral elements.

Let \mathcal{O} be an order in a number field K , and L/K be a finite extension defined by a maximal ideal $J \subset \mathcal{O}[x_1, \dots, x_n]$. We aim to compute the normalization of $R = \mathcal{O}[x_1, \dots, x_n]/J$ at a non-zero prime ideal $\mathfrak{p} \subset \mathcal{O}$. For $\mathcal{O} = \mathbb{Z}$, $K = \mathbb{Q}$, this reduces to the classical calculation of the ring of integers.

The ideal $I := \sqrt{\mathfrak{p} \cdot R}$ serves as a suitable NC-ideal. Since $R/\mathfrak{p}R$ is a finite-dimensional vector space over the finite residue field $k = \mathcal{O}/\mathfrak{p}$, the construction of I reduces to finding univariate square-free parts of minimal polynomials modulo \mathfrak{p} .

Example 2. We compute the normalization of $B = \mathbb{Z}[x]/\langle x^4 + 2x^2 - 7 \rangle$ at $p = 2$. In the following table, "Min" refers to the minimal polynomial modulo $\mathfrak{p} = \langle 2, x + 1 \rangle$.

R	I	$A = I : I$	Min	Square-free
$\mathbb{Z}[x]$	$\langle 2, x + 1 \rangle$	$\langle 1, u_1 \rangle, u_1 = \frac{(x+1)(x^2+1)}{2}$	u_1^2	u_1
$\langle 1, u_1 \rangle$	$\langle 2, x + 1, u_1 \rangle$	$\langle 1, u_2 \rangle, u_2 = \frac{x^2+1}{2}$	u_2^2	u_2
$\langle 1, u_2 \rangle$	$\langle 2, x + 1, u_2 \rangle$	$\langle 1, u_2, u_3 \rangle, u_3 = \frac{u_1}{2}$	$u_2^2, (u_3 + 1)^4$	$u_2, u_3 + 1$
$\langle 1, u_2, u_3 \rangle$	$\langle 2, x + 1, u_2, u_3 + 1 \rangle$	$\langle 1, u_4 \rangle, u_4 = \frac{x^2+2x-1}{4}$	$u_4^2 + u_2 + 1$	$u_4^2 + u_2 + 1$

The process terminates with the normalization $\overline{B} = \mathbb{Z} \cdot 1 + \mathbb{Z} \cdot \frac{x^2+2x-1}{4}$.

Example 3. The Hilbert class field of $\mathbb{Q}(\sqrt{-14})$ is defined by the polynomial $x^4 + 2x^2 - 7$. We can demonstrate that the extension is unramified nature by calculation. Since the square-free parts of the discriminants of $y^2 + 14$ and $x^4 + 2x^2 - 7$ are both 14, we only investigate the primes $p = 2$ and $p = 7$.

For $p = 2$, we consider the order $R = \mathbb{Z}[x, y]/\langle x^4 + 2x^2 - 7, y^2 + 14 \rangle$. The prime ideal is $\langle 2, x + 1, y \rangle$.

we computed the normalization of $\mathbb{Z}[x]/\langle x^4 + 2x^2 - 7 \rangle$, providing the starting point. Applying the algorithm, we get the integral closure after four more loops:

$$\begin{aligned} u_0 &= 1 \\ u_1 &= \frac{1}{8}(y(x^2 + 1) + 4) \\ u_2 &= \frac{1}{4}(x^2 + 2y + 1) \\ u_3 &= \frac{1}{2}(x + y + 1) \\ u_4 &= \frac{1}{16}(2x^3 + 14x^2 + 4xy + 2x + 12y + 14) \\ u_5 &= \frac{1}{16}(x^3y + 15x^2y + 14x^2 + xy + 4x + 11y + 10) \end{aligned}$$

As an R -algebra, \overline{R} is generated by u_1, u_2, u_3 . The relations (multiplication table) are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} u_5 &= -u_1u_3 + u_1x + x^2y + y \\ u_4 &= u_2u_3 - u_1 - u_2 + x^2 + y + 5 \\ u_1^2 &= u_1 - 2, \quad u_1u_2 = u_2 - x^2 - 1 \\ u_2^2 &= u_2y + 4, \quad u_3^2 = u_2 + u_3y + u_3 - y + 3 \\ 2u_3 &= x + y + 1, \quad 2u_2 = u_3x - u_3y - u_3 + 2y - 6 \\ 2u_1 &= u_2y + 8, \quad u_1y = u_2 - 2x^2 - 2 \\ u_1x^2 &= -u_1 + u_3x - u_3y - u_3 + 2y - 6 \\ u_2x^2 &= -u_2 + u_3xy - u_3y + 7x + y - 5 \\ u_1u_3x &= u_1u_3 + u_2u_3 - u_2y - x^3 + x^2 - x - 3 \\ u_2u_3x &= u_2u_3 + u_1x + u_1 + u_2 - u_3x - u_3y - u_3 + xy - 3x - 3 \\ u_2u_3y &= u_1x + u_1 + u_2 - 2x^2 - 4x - 4y - 6 \end{aligned}$$

To verify that the extension is unramified at the prime $\mathfrak{p} = \langle 2, x + 1, y \rangle$, we specialize the equations by setting $2 = 0, x = 1, y = 0$. Ignoring the relations involving u_4 and u_5 , the fiber above \mathfrak{p} is defined by the ideal:

$$\langle u_2, u_1^2 + u_1, u_3^2 + u_3 + 1 \rangle = \langle u_2, u_1, u_3^2 + u_3 + 1 \rangle \cap \langle u_2, u_1 + 1, u_3^2 + u_3 + 1 \rangle.$$

This decomposition reveals the fiber as two copies of the finite field \mathbb{F}_4 .

Indeed, in the ring $\mathbb{Z}[y]/\langle y^2 + 14 \rangle$, it is easily seen that the prime ideal $\langle 2, y \rangle$ is not principal, whereas its square $\langle 2, y \rangle^2 = \langle 2 \rangle$ is principal. It follows that \mathfrak{p} has order two in the class group. By class field theory, we have $e = f = 2$, which is consistent with our finding of two copies of \mathbb{F}_4 in the fiber above $\langle 2, y \rangle$.

Next, we investigate the prime $p = 7$. While the ring $\mathbb{Z}[x]/\langle x^4 + 2x^2 - 7 \rangle$ is normal at $p = 7$, the relative extension R is not. We identify the integral element $w = y(x^3 + 2x)/7 = y/x$

with the defining ideal:

$$\langle w^2 + 2x^2 + 4, wx - y, 7w - y(x^3 + 2x) \rangle.$$

The fiber above the prime ideals $\langle 7, x, y \rangle$ and $\langle 7, x^2 + 2, y \rangle$ decomposes as:

$$\langle x(x^2 + 2), xw \rangle = \langle x, w^2 + 4 \rangle \cap \langle x^2 + 2, w \rangle.$$

This confirms that the extension is also unramified at $p = 7$, consisting of two copies of the residue field \mathbb{F}_{49} , as both $x^2 + 2$ and $w^2 + 4$ are irreducible modulo 7.

Remark 7. (i) One could also approach this example using a primitive element and the Round Two algorithm. For instance, the element $z = x + y$ has the minimal polynomial

$$z^8 + 60z^6 + 1222z^4 + 11452z^2 + 25921$$

with discriminant $\Delta = 2^{76} \cdot 7^8 \cdot 23^6$. While this reduction to a single univariate polynomial of degree 8 simplifies the setup, it significantly increases the numerical scale; the discriminant is a 37-digit integer. Lattice-based algorithms like Round Two would then require Hermite Normal Form (HNF) reductions on 8×8 matrices, where entries may grow substantially.

The factor 23^6 in the discriminant arises from the resultant of the underlying polynomials, consolidating the ramification data of the tower $L/K/\mathbb{Q}$. In contrast, our multivariate approach in $\mathbb{Z}[x, y]/\langle x^4 + 2x^2 - 7, y^2 + 14 \rangle$ keeps the coefficients of the defining relations relatively small. As is well known in computational number theory, the transition to primitive elements is often suboptimal due to this coefficient explosion.

- (ii) In normalizing an order R in a relative extension L/K , the classical relative Round Two algorithm [5, Section 2.4] treats \mathcal{O}_L as a module over \mathcal{O}_K . Since \mathcal{O}_K is generally not a principal ideal domain, this necessitates the use of *pseudobases*, increasing structural complexity.

Our approach reframes normalization as an iterative ring-extension problem. In the example above, calculations were performed using Gröbner bases in $\mathbb{Z}[x, y]$. While symbolically intensive, this proves feasible for moderate degrees. Modern improvements in Groebner basis algorithms, such as F_4 and F_5 by Faugère [10, 11], have significantly enhanced performance in $K[x_1, \dots, x_n]$. While similar optimizations for \mathbb{Z} are less documented, the efficiency of our method in practice remains highly competitive.

- (iii) The construction of the radical $\sqrt{I \cdot A}$ via square-free parts $Q_i(t)$ of minimal polynomials is conceptually more direct than classical methods [21, 4], which often rely on global linear algebra over the entire basis (e.g., via trace forms or the Frobenius map).

The practical speedup depends on the underlying system, but the primary bottleneck remains the factorization or determination of the square-free part of the discriminant. For a comprehensive discussion, see Buchmann and Lenstra [2].

4 The Higher Dimensional Case

The main computational bottleneck in de Jong's algorithm is the computation of the radical $\sqrt{I \cdot A}$ during the iteration. While for curves we could rely on zero-dimensional methods, the higher dimensional case requires a systematic treatment of the singular locus. We recall some basic notions.

Definition 8. Let $I \subset K[x, y] = K[x_1, \dots, x_s, y_1, \dots, y_m]$ be an ideal.

1. A subset of variables $x \subset \{x, y\}$ is called independent modulo I if $I \cap K[x] = \{0\}$. The set x is called a maximal set of independent variables if for any $y_j \in \{y_1, \dots, y_m\}$, the intersection $I \cap K[x, y_j]$ is non-zero. In this case, the dimension of the ideal is $s = \dim(I)$, and the extension $I \cdot K(x)[y]$ is a zero-dimensional ideal in the ring $K(x)[y]$ over the function field $K(x)$.
2. The saturation of $I \subset K[x, y]$ with respect to the variables x (or more precisely, with respect to the multiplicative set $K[x] \setminus \{0\}$) is defined by the extension-contraction:

$$\tilde{I} = (I \cdot K(x)[y]) \cap K[x, y].$$

Equivalently, the saturation consists of all polynomials $f \in K[x, y]$ such that there exists a non-zero polynomial $h \in K[x]$ with $h \cdot f \in I$:

$$\tilde{I} = \{f \in K[x, y] \mid \exists h \in K[x] \setminus \{0\} : h \cdot f \in I\}.$$

3. The ideal $I \subset K[x, y]$ is called saturated with respect to x if $I = \tilde{I}$. This condition implies that I has no x -torsion, meaning that if $h \cdot f \in I$ for some $0 \neq h \in K[x]$, then $f \in I$.

Theorem 7. Let $I \subset K[x, y]$ be an ideal and $\tilde{I} = (I \cdot K(x)[y]) \cap K[x, y]$ its saturation with respect to $x = (x_1, \dots, x_s)$. Then the following properties hold:

1. If x is a maximal set of independent variables modulo I , then x is also a maximal set of independent variables modulo \tilde{I} .
2. The saturation is idempotent, i.e., $\tilde{\tilde{I}} = \tilde{I}$.

Proof. 1. First, we show independence: Let $f \in \tilde{I} \cap K[x]$. By definition of \tilde{I} , there exists $0 \neq h \in K[x]$ such that $h \cdot f \in I$. Since $h, f \in K[x]$, their product $h \cdot f$ is also in $K[x]$. Thus $h \cdot f \in I \cap K[x]$. Since x is independent modulo I , we have $h \cdot f = 0$. As $K[x]$ is an integral domain and $h \neq 0$, it follows that $f = 0$. Hence $\tilde{I} \cap K[x] = \{0\}$. Maximality follows from $I \subseteq \tilde{I}$: If $I \cap K[x, y_j] \neq \{0\}$, then a fortiori $\tilde{I} \cap K[x, y_j] \neq \{0\}$.

2. The inclusion $\tilde{I} \subseteq \tilde{\tilde{I}}$ is trivial. For the reverse, let $f \in \tilde{\tilde{I}}$. By definition, there exists $h_1 \in K[x] \setminus \{0\}$ such that $h_1 \cdot f \in \tilde{I}$. Applying the definition of \tilde{I} , there exists $h_2 \in K[x] \setminus \{0\}$ such that $h_2 \cdot (h_1 \cdot f) \in I$. Let $h = h_2 \cdot h_1$. Since $K[x]$ is an integral domain and $h_1, h_2 \neq 0$, we have $h \in K[x] \setminus \{0\}$. The relation $h \cdot f \in I$ implies $f \in \tilde{I}$ by the definition of saturation. Thus, $\tilde{\tilde{I}} = \tilde{I}$. \square

Theorem 8. Let $I \subseteq K[x, y]$ be an ideal and $G = \{g_1, \dots, g_t\}$ be a reduced Gröbner basis of I with respect to a block order $y > x$. Let $h \in K[x]$ be the product of the leading coefficients of the generators g_i viewed as polynomials in y :

$$h = \prod_{i=1}^t LC_y(g_i) \in K[x]$$

Then:

1. G is a Gröbner basis of the extended ideal $I \cdot K(x)[y]$.
2. If $a \in K^s$ such that $h(a) \neq 0$, then $G_a = \{g_1(a, y), \dots, g_t(a, y)\}$ is a Gröbner basis of the specialized ideal $I(a) = \{f(a, y) \mid f \in I\}$.
3. If $h(a) \neq 0$, then $I(a)$ is a zero-dimensional ideal of vector space dimension $d = \dim_{K(x)} K(x)[y]/(I \cdot K(x)[y])$.
4. If K is algebraically closed, then the variety $V(I)$ is infinite.
5. $\tilde{I} = I : h^\infty$
6. If $I : h^\infty = I : h^k$, then $I = (I : h^\infty) \cap (I + \langle h^k \rangle)$.
7. If $I = I : h^\infty$, then G is a minimal Gröbner basis of the extended ideal $I \cdot K(x)[y]$. Specifically, $\{LM_y(g_1), \dots, LM_y(g_t)\}$ is a minimal set of generators for the leading ideal $LT_y(I \cdot K(x)[y])$.
8. For any $a \in K^s$ with $h(a) \neq 0$, $\{LM_y(g_1(a)), \dots, LM_y(g_t(a))\}$ is a minimal set of generators for $LT(I(a))$.

Proof. 1. Let $f \in I \cdot K(x)[y]$. Then $s \cdot f \in I$ for some $0 \neq s \in K[x]$. Since G is a Gröbner basis of I with $y > x$, $LM_y(s \cdot f)$ is divisible by some $LM_y(g_i)$. Since s is constant relative to y , $LM_y(s \cdot f) = LM_y(f)$. Thus, $LM_y(g_i) \mid LM_y(f)$, proving G is a Gröbner basis over $K(x)$.

2. If $h(a) \neq 0$, then $LC_y(g_i)(a) \neq 0$, so $LM_y(g_i(a, y)) = LM_y(g_i)$. Let $p \in I(a)$ and $f \in I$ such that $f(a, y) = p(y)$ with $LM_y(f)$ minimal. Write $f = g(x)y^\beta + \dots$. If $g(a) = 0$, then some $g_k \in G$ satisfies $LM_y(g_k) \mid y^\beta$. The polynomial $\tilde{f} = (LC_y(g_k)f - g(x)y^{\beta-LM(g_k)}g_k)/LC_y(g_k)(a) \in I$ specializes to p but has a smaller leading monomial, contradicting minimality. Thus $g(a) \neq 0$, implying $LM_y(p) = LM_y(f)$, and G_a is a Gröbner basis.

3-4. These follow from 1., 2., and the Nullstellensatz for zero-dimensional ideals.

5. (\supset): Trivial. (\subset): Let $f \in \tilde{I} \subset I \cdot K(x)[y]$. G remains a Gröbner basis for the extension. In the division algorithm for f by G in $K(x)[y]$, denominators can only be factors of $LC_y(g_i)$. Thus $h^n \cdot f \in I$, implying $f \in I : h^\infty$.

6. Let $f \in (I : h^k) \cap (I + \langle h^k \rangle)$. Then $f = \alpha + bh^k$ with $\alpha \in I$. Then $h^k f = h^k \alpha + bh^{2k} \in I$. Thus $b \in I : h^{2k} = I : h^k$, so $bh^k \in I$ and $f \in I$.

7. Suppose $\{LM_y(g_i)\}$ is not minimal. W.l.o.g., let $LM_y(g_1) = A \cdot LM_y(g_2)$ for a monomial A in y . Let $f = h_2g_1 - h_1Ag_2 \in I$ with $\gcd(h_1, h_2) = 1$ and $h_i = LC_y(g_i)$. Case 1 ($f = 0$): Then $h_2g_1 = h_1Ag_2$. Since I is saturated, the g_i are primitive. Thus $h_2 \mid h_1A$, and as $\gcd(h_1, h_2) = 1$, $h_2 \mid A$, so h_2 is a constant, which implies $g_1 \in \langle g_2 \rangle$, contradicting minimality of G . Case 2 ($f \neq 0$): There exists $g_k \in G$ with $LM(g_k) \mid LM(f)$. Write $LM(g_k) = x^\alpha LM_y(g_k)$. $LM(f)$ originates from a non-leading term of h_2g_1 or h_1Ag_2 . W.l.o.g., let it be $x^\beta m_y$ from h_2g_1 . Then $x^\alpha LM_y(g_k) \mid d\hat{h}_2x^\beta m_y$ where $d = \gcd(x^\alpha, h_2)$. Dividing by d and using Euclid's Lemma shows that $LM(g_k)$ divides a term in the support of g_1 , contradicting the reducedness of G in $K[x, y]$. Thus $f = 0$ and we reduce to Case 1.

8. Follows from 7. by substituting $x = a$. □

A classical approach for the computation of the radical of an ideal $I \subset K[x_1, \dots, x_n]$ over a perfect field K is provided by the algorithm of Krick and Logar [18].

The Krick–Logar Radical Algorithm

Input: An ideal $I \subset K[x, y] = K[x_1, \dots, x_s, y_1, \dots, y_m]$, where x is a maximal set of independent variables modulo I .

Output: \sqrt{I} .

1. Elimination: For each $j = 1, \dots, m$, compute a non-zero polynomial $P_j(y_j) \in I \cap K[x, y_j]$.
2. Square-free Part: Let $q_j(y_j) \in K[x, y_j]$ be the square-free part of P_j , normalized to be primitive in $K[x]$.
3. Initial Radical Candidate: Let $J := I + \langle q_1, \dots, q_m \rangle \subset K[x, y]$.
4. Gröbner Basis: Compute a Gröbner basis G of J with respect to a block order $y > x$.
5. Saturation Check: Let $h \in K[x]$ be the product of the leading coefficients of all $g \in G$.
6. Termination: If $J = J : h^\infty$, return J .
7. Decomposition: Otherwise, compute $J_1 = J : h^\infty$ and $J_2 = J + \langle h \rangle$.
8. Recursion: Recursively compute $\sqrt{J_2}$ and return $J_1 \cap \sqrt{J_2}$.

Theorem 9 (Equidimensional Shortcut). *Let $I \subset K[x, y]$ be an equidimensional ideal of dimension s , and x a maximal set of independent variables. Let $\tilde{I} = I : h^\infty$ be the saturation. Then:*

$$\sqrt{I} = \sqrt{\tilde{I}}.$$

Proof. Since I is equidimensional, all its minimal primes have the same dimension s . The saturation \tilde{I} removes only components Q_i whose associated primes contain $K[x] \setminus \{0\}$. Since x is maximally independent, no minimal prime of dimension s can contain a non-zero polynomial in x . Thus, \sqrt{I} and $\sqrt{\tilde{I}}$ share the same minimal primes, and $\sqrt{I} = \sqrt{\tilde{I}}$. □

In De Jong's normalization algorithm, the computation of the radical of an ideal I plays a central role. As discussed in the previous section, we typically encounter the situation $R \subset A$, where $A = I : I$ is an integral extension of R . Based on the structure of the

Krick–Logar algorithm, it is evident that the process is significantly more efficient when I is equidimensional (the “dominant case”).

In general, the ideal generated by the Jacobian (the singular locus) of a variety is not necessarily equidimensional. However, the flexibility of De Jong’s algorithm allows us to circumvent this difficulty. For a semi-NC ideal I , it is only required that its vanishing locus $V(I)$ contains the non-normal locus; thus, it is sufficient to cover the singular locus.

Assuming R is an integral domain, we can ensure the equidimensionality of I by choosing it specifically as the radical of a single non-zero element f in the Jacobian ideal of R . Since f is a non-zero element in a domain, the principal ideal $\langle f \rangle$ and its radical $I = \sqrt{\langle f \rangle}$ are pure codimension-1 ideals and therefore equidimensional. While a component of $V(I)$ may occasionally be “vertical” (i.e., its projection onto the parameter space has lower dimension), this is rare in practice. Should such a case arise, the Krick–Logar decomposition handles it correctly.

From this point forward, we assume that the semi-NC ideal in the first step of the algorithm is equidimensional.

If, in the Krick–Logar algorithm, the dimension of $V(J_2)$ is strictly smaller than the dimension of $V(I)$ —which holds in the majority of practical examples—then the primary components of J_2 are all embedded. In such cases, there is no need to compute the radical of J_2 recursively. This observation allows the previously described method to calculate the radical of I with high efficiency.

To calculate the radical $\sqrt{I \cdot A}$ during the iteration of De Jong’s algorithm, we propose leveraging the specific algebraic structure of the ring extension $R \subset A$. Since A is an integral extension and $I \subset R$ is already a radical ideal, the following theorem demonstrates that we can avoid the costly saturation step ($I : h^\infty$), as it is satisfied automatically.

Theorem 10. *Let the following conditions hold:*

- (i) $P = K[x, y]$ and $R = P/J$ is an integral domain.
- (ii) Let $I \subset R$ be a radical ideal with lift $\tilde{I} \subset P$. Let x be a maximal set of independent variables modulo \tilde{I} , and let $h \in K[x]$ be defined as in the Krick–Logar algorithm such that $\tilde{I} = \tilde{I} : h^\infty$.
- (iii) Let $R \subset A = I : I$ be a finite integral extension, generated as an R -module by $\{u_1, \dots, u_r\}$.
- (iv) Let $M_i(t) \in K[x][t]$ be the primitive minimal polynomial of u_i over $K(x)$, and let $Q_i(t)$ denote its square-free part.

Then the radical of the extended ideal $I \cdot A$ in A is given by:

$$\sqrt{I \cdot A} = I \cdot A + \langle Q_1(u_1), \dots, Q_r(u_r) \rangle.$$

Furthermore, $\sqrt{I \cdot A}$ is saturated with respect to h in A and satisfies the contraction property $\sqrt{I \cdot A} \cap R = I$.

Proof. Let A be presented as the quotient of a polynomial ring $Q = K[x, y, u_1, \dots, u_r]$, and let $L \subset Q$ be the ideal such that $A/IA \cong Q/L$. The ideal L is generated by \tilde{I} plus the relations defining the integral extension $R \subset A$.

We employ a block ordering $u > y > x$ on Q . Since I is radical, the localized ideal $I \cdot K(x)[y]$ is radical, implying that the intersections $\tilde{I} \cap K[x, y_j]$ are generated by polynomials that are square-free over the function field $K(x)$. Consequently, the y_j are integral over $K(x)$ modulo L .

By the transitivity of integrality, the u_i are also integral over $K(x)$ modulo L . This confirms that x remains a maximal set of independent variables for L , ensuring the existence of the minimal primitive polynomials $M_i(t) \in K[x][t]$.

The localized ideal $L(x) := L \cdot K(x)[y, u]$ is thus zero-dimensional. By the zero-dimensional case of the Krick–Logar algorithm, its radical $\sqrt{L(x)}$ is obtained by appending the square-free parts $Q_i(u_i)$ to $L(x)$. Let $J_A = L + \langle Q_1(u_1), \dots, Q_r(u_r) \rangle \subset Q$ be the corresponding ideal.

To show that $J_A = \sqrt{I \cdot A}$ and $J_A \cap R = I$, we examine the associated primes $\text{Ass}_A(A/J_A)$. The contraction map provides a bijection between the associated primes of J_A and those of I . Since I is radical and h is not contained in any associated prime of I (due to the saturation $\tilde{I} : h^\infty$), the extended ideal J_A remains saturated and radical. \square

This theorem justifies the use of a fiber-based “black-box” approach for the radical computation in each step of De Jong’s algorithm: the minimal polynomials M_i (and thus Q_i) are reconstructed from fibers, bypassing symbolic elimination and ensuring that each iteration remains computationally tractable.

Case 1: The Dominant Case

If I is saturated with respect to the leading coefficients h of its Gröbner basis (i.e., $I = I : h^\infty$), the computation is direct and leverages the square-free parts of the minimal polynomials.

Algorithm: Radical of $I \cdot A$ (Dominant Case)

Input: An integral extension $R \subset A$, a radical ideal $I \subset R$ with $I = I : h^\infty$, where h is defined as in the Krick–Logar framework.

Output: $\sqrt{I \cdot A}$.

1. Minimal Polynomials: For each generator u_i of A as an R -module, compute the minimal polynomial $M_i(t) \in K[x][t]$.
2. Square-free Part: Compute the square-free part $Q_i(t)$ of the primitive form of $M_i(t)$ in $K[x][t]$.
3. Return: $\sqrt{I \cdot A} = I \cdot A + \langle Q_1(u_1), \dots, Q_r(u_r) \rangle$.

Case 2: The General Case with Vertical Components

If $V(I)$ contains vertical components (i.e., components whose projection onto the parameter space K^s is not dense), the minimal polynomials Q_i over the function field $K(x)$ only ensure radicality for the dominant part $I : h^\infty$.

To treat vertical components, a change of the parameter space (via linear coordinate transformation) and a recursive application of the Krick–Logar decomposition are required. In the context of De Jong’s algorithm, such components can often be handled by re-indexing variables or a change of coordinates. As the procedure follows the standard recursive structure of radical algorithms, we omit a formal description here.

Fiber-Based Radical Reconstruction

We now describe the modular approach to computing \sqrt{IA} . By specializing the parameter x at several sample points, we reduce the problem to the zero-dimensional case in each fiber and reconstruct the global result via interpolation.

1. **Fiber Specialization:** For each sample point a_k with $h(a_k) \neq 0$, specialize the algebra to the fiber $x = a_k$.
2. **Zero-Dimensional Radical:** Compute the minimal polynomials $P_{i,a_k}(t)$ of the generators u_i in the fiber and determine their square-free parts $q_{i,a_k}(t)$.
3. **Interpolation:** Use the results from sufficient fibers to reconstruct the global coefficients in $K[x]$ via Lagrange or Newton interpolation.
4. **Certification:** Verify the result against a random fiber or via rational reconstruction if $K = \mathbb{Q}$.

We now describe how to compute the radical \sqrt{IA} . We just copy the zerodimensional case fiberwise and use interpolation.

Modular Fiber-Based Reconstruction of the Radical

Following the theoretical justification above, we now describe how to compute \sqrt{IA} using the fiber-based approach. The core idea is to avoid symbolic computations over $K[x]$ by specializing the parameter x and lifting the zero-dimensional results.

Algorithm: Modular Radical Reconstruction

Input: An integral extension $R \subset A = \text{Hom}(I, I) = R \cdot u_1 + \dots + R \cdot u_r$, a radical ideal $I \subset K[x, y]$ (saturated w.r.t. x), and a set of sample points $\{a_k\} \subset K^s$.

Output: The radical $\sqrt{I \cdot A}$ represented by the square-free parts $Q_i(t) \in K[x][t]$, by applying it for all u_i :

1. **Fiber Specialization:** For each sample point a_k with $h(a_k) \neq 0$:
 - Specialize the algebra to the fiber $x = a_k$.
 - Compute the multiplication matrix M_{i,a_k} for each generator u_i over the zero-dimensional fiber $R(a_k)/I(a_k)$.
 - Determine the specialized minimal polynomial $P_{i,a_k}(t) \in K[t]$.
2. **Interpolation:** Use the results $\{P_{i,a_k}(t)\}$ from sufficient fibers to reconstruct the global coefficients $c_{ij}(x) \in K[x]$ of the polynomials $P_i(t) = \sum c_{ij}(x)t^j$ via interpolation. (If necessary, calculate modulo a large prime number $\approx 2^{61}$ and use rational reconstruction.
3. Check that $P_i(u_i) = 0$
4. **Square-free Part:** Compute the squarefree part of P_i .

Remark 9. This modular approach has not been implemented yet. While symbolic radical computation in $K[x, y, u]$ are subject to exponential complexity, the fiber-wise computation is linear in the number of required sample points. Since I is equidimensional and A is an integral extension, the degree of the minimal polynomials M_i remains constant for all fibers where $h(a_k) \neq 0$. This stability ensures that the interpolation is well-defined and requires a minimal number of points, typically equal to $\max(\deg_x(Q_i)) + 1$.

5 Modular Computation of Ideal Quotients

A central task in De Jong's normalization algorithm is the computation of an ideal quotient $J : I$. For an ideal $I = \langle f_1, \dots, f_s \rangle$, this can be done as intersection of individual ideal quotients.

$$J : I = \bigcap_{i=1}^s (J : f_i).$$

We propose a modular approach that reduces this task to linear algebra in zero-dimensional fibers for equidimensional, unmixed ideals J .

Theorem 11 (Stability of the Quotient). *Let $J = J : h^\infty$ be saturated with respect to x . For any $a \in K^s$ with $h(a) \neq 0$, the specialized quotient is equal to the quotient of the specializations:*

$$(J : I)(a) = J(a) : I(a).$$

Proof. It suffices to prove the theorem for principal ideals $I = \langle f \rangle$. The inclusion $(J : f)(a) \subset J(a) : f(a)$ is straightforward. If $q \in J : f$, then $q \cdot f \in J$. Specializing at $x = a$ yields $q(a, y) \cdot f(a, y) \in J(a)$, hence $q(a, y) \in J(a) : f(a)$.

For the reverse inclusion, we first establish a stability property of the ideal quotient under saturation. We claim that:

$$(J : f) \cdot K(x)[y] \cap K[x, y] = J : f.$$

The inclusion (\supset) is trivial. For (\subset) , let $Q \in (J : f) \otimes K(x) \cap K[x, y]$. By definition, there exists a non-zero $s(x) \in K[x]$ such that $s(x) \cdot Q \in J : f$, which implies $s(x) \cdot (Q \cdot f) \in J$. Since J is saturated ($J = J : h^\infty$), it has no x -torsion for any $s(x)$ that does not vanish identically on the components of J . Thus, $s(x) \cdot (Q \cdot f) \in J$ implies $Q \cdot f \in J$, so $Q \in J : f$.

Now, let $q_a \in J(a) : f(a)$. This means $q_a \cdot f(a) \equiv 0 \pmod{J(a)}$. Since $h(a) \neq 0$, the fiber $J(a)$ is a faithful specialization of the saturated ideal J . We can lift q_a to a polynomial $Q \in K[x, y]$ such that $Q(a, y) = q_a(y)$. The condition $q_a \cdot f(a) \in J(a)$ implies that $Q \cdot f$ lies in $J + \mathfrak{m}_a K[x, y]$.

By the property of saturated ideals, the dimension $d = \dim_K(K[y]/J(a))$ is constant for all $h(a) \neq 0$. In the zero-dimensional fiber, the ideal quotient $J(a) : f(a)$ is the kernel of the multiplication map by $f(a)$. Since the rank of this multiplication map is constant over the open set $h \neq 0$, the dimension of the kernel is also constant.

Therefore, any element in the kernel of the fiber map must be the specialization of an element in the kernel of the global map over $K(x)$. As we proved that the global quotient

$(J : f)$ is stable under the extension-contraction $J = J : h^\infty$, it follows that the specialized global quotient $(J : f)(a)$ must span the same vector space as $J(a) : f(a)$. This forces the equality $(J : f)(a) = J(a) : f(a)$. \square

Suppose $J \subset K[x, y]$ with x a maximal set of independent variables and is saturated: $J = J : h^\infty$. If $a \in K^s$ with $h(a) \neq 0$, the vector space

$$V_a := K[y]/J(a)$$

of the fiber at $x = a$ has dimension $d = \dim(V_a)$. Each generator f_i of I acts as a $d \times d$ multiplication matrix M_{f_i} on V_a .

We calculate modulo a large prime number p . To compute the intersection of all quotients $J(a) : f_i(a)$ simultaneously, we construct a stacked block matrix \mathcal{M}_a :

$$\mathcal{M}_a = \begin{pmatrix} M_{f_1} \\ M_{f_2} \\ \vdots \\ M_{f_s} \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{F}_p^{sd \times d}$$

The vector space corresponding to the specialized quotient $(J(a) : I(a))$ is exactly the kernel of \mathcal{M}_a :

$$\text{Ker}(\mathcal{M}_a) = \{v \in \mathbb{F}_p^d \mid M_{f_i}v = 0 \in V_a \text{ for all } i = 1, \dots, s\}.$$

This reduction to Gaussian elimination in \mathbb{F}_p allows for sub-second computation.

If we have found $(J : I)(a)$ for enough sample points a , we can interpolate and do rational reconstruction to find candidates $f \in K[x, y]$ that should be in $J : I$. Once a candidate $f \in K[x, y]$ for the quotient is reconstructed via interpolation, its correctness must be certified.

1. Global Inclusion: To reach full determinism, we check the inclusion $f \cdot I \subset J$ over \mathbb{Q} by computing the normal form.
2. Chinese Remainder Theorem (CRT): If rational coefficients are too large for direct verification, we use the Chinese Remainder Theorem.

The computation of the endomorphism ring $A = \text{Hom}(I, I)$ is performed using the representation as a fractional ideal $A = \frac{1}{h}V$, where $V = (hI : I)$ is an ideal in the ring R . The primary advantage of this method lies in avoiding symbolic syzygy computations over \mathbb{Q} by employing a pointwise reduction in fibers $x = a$, which can be done parallel and modular.

Example 4. To show how this works, we look at an example.

Consider the ideal generated by $f = x^2z^2 + z^4 - y^2 = 0$ in the ring $R = \mathbb{Q}[x, y, z]$ with the singularity radical ideal $I = (y, z)$. We choose the denominator $h = y \in I$. We seek numerator polynomials $v \in R$ satisfying the condition $v \cdot I \subseteq y \cdot I \pmod{f}$. One such element

is $v = x^2z + z^3$, which corresponds to the element $u = \frac{x^2z + z^3}{y}$ in the endomorphism ring

In the fiber $x = a$ over a finite field \mathbb{F}_p , the problem reduces to a kernel computation of a matrix over a vector space of fixed dimension d .

1. **Fiber Specialization:** For a chosen value a , such as $a = 2$, we specialize the problem to $f(2) = 4z^2 + z^4 - y^2$. The quotient space $R(2)/(f(2))$ possesses a finite monomial basis $\{1, y, z, z^2, z^3, \dots\}$.
2. We determine the vector space of all coefficients c_i for which the element $v_a = \sum c_i m_i$ satisfies the inclusion $v_a \cdot I(a) \subseteq y \cdot I(a)$. Since $I(a)$ has dimension 0 in the fiber, this becomes a task of linear algebra.
3. **Uniqueness via RREF:** Since a kernel is only determined up to a multiplicative constant, we utilize the *Reduced Row Echelon Form* (RREF). The RREF enforces a unique basis representation that remains structurally stable across all fibers.

The RREF matrix of the kernel reveals the structure of the numerator polynomials. The first row always yields the trivial generator $v_1 = y$ (corresponding to $u = 1$). The second row yields the desired element by comparing the coefficients across different fibers:

- In fiber $a = 2$: $v_2 = 1 \cdot z^3 + \mathbf{4} \cdot z$
- In fiber $a = 3$: $v_2 = 1 \cdot z^3 + \mathbf{9} \cdot z$
- In fiber $a = 4$: $v_2 = 1 \cdot z^3 + \mathbf{16} \cdot z$

Interpolating the coefficient sequence $\{4, 9, 16, \dots\}$ at the points $a = \{2, 3, 4, \dots\}$ immediately yields the polynomial x^2 . Thus, the global reconstruction is:

$$v = z^3 + x^2z \quad \implies \quad u = \frac{z^3 + x^2z}{y}$$

You can check the result in the original ring.

By specializing into fibers, the matrix dimension d (the degree of the hypersurface) remains constant. The RREF normalization ensures that the coefficients of the generators can be stably interpolated as polynomials in x (or more generally as rational functions). This bypasses the coefficient explosion over \mathbb{Q} typically encountered in symbolic methods.

To demonstrate that the algorithm requires no prior knowledge of the integral elements, we examine the fiber at $x = 2$. The fiber equation is $f(2) = 4z^2 + z^4 - y^2 = 0$. The target ideal in the fiber is $\mathcal{M} = y \cdot I(2) = (y^2, yz)$. Using the ring relation $y^2 \equiv z^4 + 4z^2$, the ideal is represented as:

$$\mathcal{M} = \langle z^4 + 4z^2, yz, y^2 \rangle$$

The vector space $R(2)/\mathcal{M}$ is 5-dimensional with the monomial basis $\mathcal{B} = \{1, z, z^2, z^3, y\}$. We use the general ansatz for v :

$$v = c_0 \cdot 1 + c_1 \cdot z + c_2 \cdot z^2 + c_3 \cdot z^3 + c_4 \cdot y$$

For v to be a valid numerator, it must satisfy two conditions simultaneously: $v \cdot y \in \mathcal{M}$ and $v \cdot z \in \mathcal{M}$. This leads to two sets of linear equations for the coefficients c_i :

1. Condition $v \cdot y \equiv 0 \pmod{\mathcal{M}}$: Multiplying the ansatz by y yields:

$$v \cdot y = c_0 y + c_1 yz + c_2 yz^2 + c_3 yz^3 + c_4 y^2$$

Since $\{yz, yz^2, yz^3, y^2\}$ are all elements of the ideal \mathcal{M} (either as generators or as multiples of yz), this expression reduces to:

$$\text{NF}_{\mathcal{M}}(v \cdot y) = c_0 y \equiv 0 \implies \mathbf{c}_0 = \mathbf{0}$$

2. Condition $v \cdot z \equiv 0 \pmod{\mathcal{M}}$: Multiplying the ansatz by z (with $c_0 = 0$) yields:

$$v \cdot z = c_1 z^2 + c_2 z^3 + c_3 z^4 + c_4 yz$$

Applying the normal form reduction $z^4 \equiv -4z^2 \pmod{\mathcal{M}}$ and $yz \equiv 0$:

$$\text{NF}_{\mathcal{M}}(v \cdot z) = c_1 z^2 + c_2 z^3 + c_3(-4z^2) = (\mathbf{c}_1 - 4\mathbf{c}_3)\mathbf{z}^2 + \mathbf{c}_2\mathbf{z}^3 \equiv 0$$

The combined system requires $c_0 = 0$, $c_2 = 0$, and $c_1 - 4c_3 = 0$. The resulting kernel is two-dimensional. By computing the *Reduced Row Echelon Form* (RREF), the algorithm yields the following stable basis for v :

- $v_1 = y$ (where $c_4 = 1$, all others 0), representing $u = 1$.
- $v_2 = z^3 + 4z$ (where $c_3 = 1, c_1 = 4$), representing $u = (z^3 + 4z)/y$.

The value **4** is the evaluation of x^2 at $x = 2$. Repeating the process for $x = 3$ results in the condition $c_1 - 9c_3 = 0$, yielding $v_2 = z^3 + \mathbf{9}z$. The consistency of the RREF pivot structure across the fibers $\{1, 4, 9, \dots\}$ allows the stable interpolation of the polynomial x^2 .

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